

D2.2 – Enhanced interoperability of tools

Overview and availability through software repositories with documentation

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Report Overview

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Executive Summary

This report comprises part of Deliverable D2.2, which aims to develop and demonstrate how data, models and knowledge can be made interoperable and combined to enhance workflows considering disaster risk management (DRM) and climate change adaptation (CCA). The main part of this deliverable consists of enhanced tools and numerical model improvements targeting different parts of the DRM and CCA cycles that have been implemented and tested. The piloted improvements are designed with stakeholders from the four Real World Labs (RWLs) through stakeholders processes coordinated by Work Packages (WPs) 3 and 4 or based on interoperability needs identified by the stock take reported in Deliverable D2.1. The new or optimized workflows underpinned by improved and interoperable tools and models will be tested and co-evaluated in the RWLs.

Since the core of this deliverable are the interoperable tools and models themselves, the purpose of this report is to provide a common and integrated reference for these innovations, to present and certify the required advances that were co-identified with RWL stakeholders, and finally to deliver easy access to DIRECTED models, codes and software development environments by compiling a full set of links to e.g. GitHub repositories and comprehensive model documentation and tutorials.

The report covers the nine different models applied in the RWL workflows that were updated over the course of the project. The **SaferPlaces** platform integrates geospatial, satellite, climate data; and AI-based models into a cloud computing environment. **RIM2D** is a high performing hydraulic 2D computer model for the simulation of pluvial and fluvial floods; **The Danube model** is multi-hazard and risk model for the Danube region, featuring different modules including hydrology. **DamageCost** is an economic damage cost assessment tool for QGIS, **CLIMADA** is an open-source software framework for climate risk and adaptation assessment; the **Climate Connectivity Hub and Taxonomy** is an online “search and discovery” tool to help users find relevant knowledge and organizations working on climate change issues; the **Citizen VR Tool** is a new virtual reality tool developed entirely within DIRECTED based on interest from stakeholders; **ABSOLUT** is a statistical crop model to estimate yields e.g. under water stress; and finally the **Social Vulnerability Index** is a tool developed to identify communities that may be at great risk during disasters due to social factors. While the first six models are described in the Grant Agreement, the latter three were identified solely based on RWL processes.

Lastly, the Annex contains additional technical information relating to the SaferPlaces model, which is a commercially licensed tool, made available to the RWLs through the project.

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List of Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
AI	ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
API	APPLICATION PROGRAMMING INTERFACE
CCA	CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION
DEM	DIGITAL ELEVATION MODEL
DM	DANUBE MODEL
DRM	DISASTER RISK MANAGEMENT
DTU	TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF DENMARK
ECMWF	EUROPEAN CENTRE FOR MEDIUM-RANGE WEATHER FORECASTS
FAIR	FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, INTEROPERABLE AND REUSABLE
GeoJSON	FORMAT DESIGNED FOR REPRESENTING SIMPLE GEOGRAPHICAL FEATURES (BASED ON THE JSON FORMAT)
GDPR	GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION
GFZ	HELMHOLTZ CENTRE FOR GEOSCIENCES
GPU / CPU	GRAPHICS / CENTRAL PROCESSING UNIT
IoT	INTERNET OF THINGS

IPCC	INTERGOVERNMENTAL PANEL ON CLIMATE CHANGE
MCDM	MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION-MAKING
NWP	NUMERICAL WEATHER PREDICTION
OGC	OPEN GEOSPATIAL CONSORTIUM
PIK	POTSDAM INSTITUTE FOR CLIMATE IMPACT RESEARCH
RWL	REAL WORLD LAB
SO	SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES
SVI	SOCIAL VULNERABILITY INDEX
TIFF	TAGGED IMAGE FILE FORMAT
VR	VIRTUAL REALITY
WMS	WEB MAP SERVICE
WP	WORK PACKAGE
UCC	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK
UNDRR	UNITED NATIONS OFFICE FOR DISASTER RISK REDUCTION

1 Introduction

One of DIRECTED's specific objectives (SO2) is to advance the interoperability of data, models and tools, i.e. to pave the way towards improved, robust and actionable decision-support for disaster risk management (DRM) and climate change adaptation (CCA). In this light, DIRECTED aims to facilitate relevant integration of outputs within and across DRM and CCA workflows to harness their synergies and provide extended functionalities for sound decision support in multiple domains; while promoting the use of existing data sets, models and tools through enhanced and seamless exchange of information between models and consistent use of knowledge and data across all phases of the DRM and CCA cycles using open standards.

This report provides an overview of advances towards model and data interoperability carried out within DIRECTED's Work Package 2 and specifically Task 2.2. Formally starting in Year 2 of the project and following the user needs assessment integrated into the Real World Labs (RWLs) (WP1), Risk-Tandem processes (WP4) and the stock take carried out in Task 2.1, several existing tools and data sets were enhanced for interoperability and integration into, e.g. theData Fabric. Table 1 provides an overview of the models and tool advanced in DIRECTED. Models (a) to (f) were all improved based on recommendations obtained from direct interactions with RWL stakeholders and subsequent internal linkages and/or linkages with theData Fabric. Similarly, the **Citizen VR App (g)** replaced the tool originally envisaged by the DIRECTED Grant Agreement based on recommendations from RWL stakeholders, who did not find this tool useful. The Citizen VR App is an entirely new innovation, implemented from scratch in DIRECTED to serve the stakeholders of RWL-2: Emilia Romagna Region. Inclusion of the **ABSOLUT crop model (h)** and the **Social Vulnerability Index (i)** into the project's demonstration suite of models also followed from the RWL stakeholder processes (gap analysis) in RWL-3: Danube Region and RWL-1: Copenhagen and the Capital Region/RWL-2: Emilia Romagna Region, respectively. In both cases, these models were largely included "as is", demonstrating the potential of adding existing data and models in interoperable frameworks. A third model – the ForeFire fire spread model originally developed at the Université de Corse by Pascal Paoli and used by DIRECTED partners from DTU – is likely to be tested in RWL-2 and RWL-3 in the third reporting period and is not described in this report.

Table 1: Interoperable models in DIRECTED. Model enhancements were informed by interoperability and stakeholder needs. For an overview of interoperability improvements, please consult the chapters indicated to the right. The links directly to the model's main code repositories or home page. The star * indicates models or tools that were not considered in the original workplan but added on recommendations of RWL stakeholders.

Tool or model	Main innovations for interoperability	Chapter
(a) SaferPlaces Digital Twin Solution for flood risk intelligence	Developing compliance with RWLs input flood hazard/damage data (forecast and real-time). Developing output compliance with Data Fabric and (b), (d), (e).	Chapter 2 & Annex
Link: www.SaferPlaces.co		
Link: https://manual.SaferPlaces.co/manual_eng		
(b) RIM2D – a high-resolution, two-dimensional hydrodynamic model	Added functionality for using additional input data sources	Chapter 3
Link: RIM2D: https://git.gfz-potsdam.de/hydro/rfm/rim2d		
Link: RIM2D QGIS Plugins: https://git.gfz-potsdam.de/hydro/rfm/rim2d_qplug		
(c) Danube model – a combined eco-hydrological and hydrodynamic model	Several model improvements were implemented for added compliance with high-resolution flood models (a) and (b) as well as (d) and for increasing the practical value of simulations for end-users.	Chapter 4
Link: https://www.pik-potsdam.de/~wortmann/swim/swim_manual.pdf		
Link: The CaMa-Flood User Manual is available for registered users from the CaMa-Flood website: http://hydro.iis.u-tokyo.ac.jp/~yamada/cama-flood/		
(e) Damage Cost – economic, multi-sector damage cost assessment model	Added input compliance with hazard data from (a), (b), and (c). Output compliance with Data Fabric. Damage cost functions exported to CLIMADA (d).	Chapter 5
Link: https://github.com/Skadesokonomi/Dokumentation-og-vejledninger (mostly in Danish)		
Link: GitHub repository: https://github.com/Skadesokonomi		
(d) CLIMADA - probabilistic risk assessment and adaptation option appraisal tool	Adding functionality for multi-criteria inputs and analyses; imported damage cost curves from the Damage Cost model (e) for compliance.	Chapter 6
Link: Link to user guides and technical documentation		
Link: GitHub repository		
(f) Climate Connectivity Hub and Taxonomy	Enhances the interoperability of online knowledge; plug-in into Data Fabric	Chapter 7
Link: http://connectivity-hub.com/		
(g) Citizen VR App *	Interactive, simulation-based environment for citizen flood preparedness.	Chapter 8
Link: NA		
(h) ABSOLUT – statistical crop model *	A statistically-based model analysing and projecting the cause-relationship between weather features and annual crop yields in sub-regions of the modelling domain. To utilize it in RWL 3, its first pan-European setup had been established.	Chapter 9
Link: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4468608		
(i) Social Vulnerability Index (tool) *	The Social Vulnerability Index maps at regional and local scales the distribution of social vulnerability to environmental hazards including flooding and heat stress.	Chapter 10
Link: https://ucc-climpadap.github.io/SVIBook/index.html		

The innovations listed in [Table 1](#) are subject to different software licenses, and/or different terms and conditions. Some of the innovations like SaferPlaces and the Danube model are subject to restricted licenses, whereas other tools like CLIMADA and Damage Cost can be used under an open-source license. As a result, the code and documentation (which is the principal part of this deliverable) are generally accessible from the model developers' websites or alternatively from DIRECTED's GitHub repository:

https://github.com/directedproject-eu/interoperability_sandbox

Similarly, the links indicated in [Table 1](#) provide direct access to the model developers' websites or GitHub code repositories.

This report has 10 chapters, including the current overview chapter. The remaining nine chapters and the appendix are devoted to the different models and tools ([Table 1](#)). The length of the chapters reflect that these tools vary in type and complexity, yet all chapters are structured in the same manner:

- The first section offers a short **Description** of the model or tool
- The second section describes **Advancements** with respect to the current versions and functionality informed by stakeholders and practitioners (e.g. through RWL processes) or by technical and scientific interoperability requirements for enhanced workflows (code and/or methodology)
- The third section describes the **Accessibility** of the model or tool, in terms of (i) Technical documentation, (ii) Code and content, (iii) Scientific publications, and (iv) Availability (e.g. whether the code has a restricted or open license). This section specifically provides direct links to this content (if applicable).

2 SaferPlaces

The SaferPlaces platform is evolving rapidly to address the complex and growing challenges posed by climate-related flood risks in both urban and coastal areas. Under the scope of the DIRECTED project, SaferPlaces has been configured and interfaced with the DIRECTED environment to enhance interoperability, support real-time flood intelligence, and enable seamless integration with On-Site Real Observation and Forecasting models within the DIRECTED Data Fabric ([Figure 1](#)). These developments are designed to unlock the potential for innovation across the 4 RWLs by embedding flood risk knowledge into local decision-making processes and data ecosystems.

2.1 Description

SaferPlaces is a commercially-licensed tool developed by GECOSistema (Background IPR) as a cloud-based platform that supports urban planners, civil protection authorities, and insurers in assessing and mitigating flood risk through a suite of advanced tools and APIs. Its modular architecture includes a range of embedded models tailored to different flooding scenarios. SaferRAIN evaluates pluvial (rainfall-induced) flood hazards using high-resolution urban topography and rainfall data. SaferCOAST simulates coastal flood risk under sea level rise and storm surge scenarios. SaferRIVER integrates river hydrology and hydraulics for fluvial flood modelling. The platform also incorporates the UNTRIM hydrodynamic engine for complex 2D/3D simulations of fluvial, pluvial and coastal and estuarine systems. Finally, SaferDAMAGE estimates flood-related economic losses by integrating hazard maps with land use and exposure data.

All components are accessible via a powerful API, enabling seamless integration into external applications and decision-support systems. See Annex.

2.2 Advancements

Figure 1: Example of integration of SaferPlaces inside the Data Fabric for pluvial real-time flood feed by radar rainfall maps. Source: <https://directed-rwl2.SaferPlaces.co/pluvial-real-time>

In terms of data and model interoperability, the main challenge is to enable external systems and stakeholders to leverage SaferPlace' advanced flood modeling capabilities through an open, modular and interoperable architecture. This is pursued primarily by exposing and configuring robust APIs for accessing hazard and damage models, while ensuring semantic and syntactic compatibility with the DIRECTED Data Fabric, allowing data exchange across platforms.

Another strategic goal identified by stakeholders is to enable real-time and predictive data ingestion capabilities (Figure 1), applying SaferPlaces as a dynamic decision-support tool for emergency and disaster risk management .

Finally, the deployment is oriented to supporting new applications for climate adaptation, critical infrastructure resilience, and community early warning systems in the RWLs.

Real-Time and Forecast Data Integration

During the project, SaferPlaces was configured and interfaced to ingest real-time and forecast-based data in its simulations, leveraging its modeling and predictive capabilities in forecasting-nowcasting. The platform now ingests numerical weather prediction (NWP) outputs from global providers such as ECMWF and from national services to simulate future rainfall scenarios and to trigger flood-hazard simulations as weather conditions evolve.

For coastal applications, SaferPlaces acquires sea-level and storm-surge forecasts that feed anticipatory modeling of coastal flooding through the SaferCOAST and UNTRIM modules ([Figure 2](#)).

Figure 2: Example of connection of SaferCOAST coastal flood modeling routine with sea level data for coastal flood simulation, <https://directed-rwl2.SaferPlaces.co/coastal-realtime-forecast>

In parallel, the acquisition of real-time radar precipitation supports radar-based rainfall nowcasting within the SaferRAIN module, enabling rapid updates of urban flood risk as convective systems develop, which strengthens short-term decision-making for emergency services and urban managers.

Accordingly, the deployment operates in both anticipatory (forecast-driven) and responsive (nowcast-driven) modes, providing enhanced situational awareness across time horizons.

API-Enabled Core Modules

The exposure and configuration of RESTful APIs across SaferPlaces modules enables flexible and automated access to simulation and risk assessment capabilities. The module SaferRAIN simulates urban pluvial flood scenarios based on forecast or observed rainfall data. APIs allow triggering simulations, retrieving flood maps, and visualizing time series outputs.

SaferRIVER supports integration of hydrological models and real-time hydrographs to simulate river flooding, with an API suitable for connections to national hydro-meteorological services or IoT stream gauges.

For coastal domains, SaferCOAST and UNTRIM deliver high-resolution coastal-flood modeling enhanced with sea-level forecasts; their APIs support scenario configuration,

spatial querying, and map generation. SaferDAMAGE computes potential economic losses using vulnerability functions and now supports dynamic loss estimation based on real-time hazard scenarios, which is valuable for crisis management.

A central role is played by SaferData, the data collection and pre-processing system developed to provide continuously updated information on current weather conditions and short-term forecasts.

This system was designed to:

- **Collect data** periodically from multiple providers, including radar observations, rainfall monitoring sensors, river level gauging stations, and marine observation systems (wave height and sea level).
- **Organize and store the data** in a structured way, ensuring efficient and secure access through centralized storage.
- **Support visualization and analysis** of information via an interactive web platform, as well as provide input for advanced simulation models and forecasting systems.

In practice, SaferData serves as a centralized data hub, enabling interoperability and facilitating the use of both real-time and forecast data to support critical decision-making processes in disaster risk management.

The project integration repository (process definitions, runtime payloads, and scheduling logic) is maintained in a private GitHub repository, as the *Technical Appendix – API Definitions & RWL Usage* for the detailed API specifications and production usage in the Rimini Real-World Lab.

All APIs are designed with standard geospatial formats (GeoJSON, TIFF, WMS) and are interoperable with the semantic structure of the DIRECTED Data Fabric.

Integration with the DIRECTED Data Fabric

An API-first design has facilitated the integration and interfacing with the DIRECTED Data Fabric, a federated data infrastructure that supports cross-sector interoperability.

Through this integration, third-party tools used in the RWLs can trigger simulations directly via APIs; hazard and damage layers can be published as linked data exposed via SPARQL and REST endpoints; and metadata can be enriched and harmonized using shared taxonomies and ontologies such as INSPIRE and SOSA/SSN.

This enables a seamless workflow in which e.g. local rainfall radar data can be ingested, SaferRAIN simulations can be executed, and outputs can be visualized within the RWL planning dashboard, typically within minutes.

2.3 Accessibility

Technical documentation, code and content:

The OpenAPI specification for SaferPlaces is available at:

<http://pygeoapi-SaferPlaces-lb-409838694.us-east-1.elb.amazonaws.com/openapi>

It describes resources, parameters, schemas, and response models for the OGC API processes endpoints and can be used with standard OpenAPI clients to explore and test requests. Additional information is available at

- www.SaferPlaces.co
- https://manual.SaferPlaces.co/manual_eng

Scientific publications

The API and its processors are grounded in peer-reviewed work on pluvial and coastal flood modelling and on the UNTRIM engine.

- <https://SaferPlaces.co/scientifically-proven-hazard-and-damage-modelling/>
- See: Samela C. et al. (2020); Essenfelder A.H. et al. (2022); Staccione A., Essenfelder A.H., Bagli S., Mysiak J. (2024); Kyaw K.K. et al. (2024); Mamo L.T. et al. (2022); Ballinger R.C., Dodds W. (2020); Cheng R.T., Casulli V. (2002); MacWilliams M.L. et al. (2007); Jankowski J.A., Patzwahl R., Platzek F.W. (2016); Forest Valley (2024). Follow the link for full references.
- For recent updates on publications: [\[1\]](#)[\[2\]](#)[\[3\]](#)

These resources provide comprehensive insights into the technologies and methodologies associated with SaferPlaces, SaferRain, SaferCoast, and the UNTRIM model.

Availability

The SaferPlaces API is part of a commercial solution developed and maintained by GECOSistema and its partners. Within the context of the DIRECTED project, access to the API has been granted on a restricted, non-commercial basis. Licenses are made available exclusively for the purpose of integration and testing within the DIRECTED Data Fabric and are strictly limited to activities conducted within the four RWLs. This special licensing framework is intended to support collaborative research, prototype development, and data interoperability testing. Any commercial exploitation, external redistribution, or third-party resale of the API services is explicitly excluded under the current agreement. Entities

interested in broader or commercial use of SaferPlaces technology are invited to contact the development team for dedicated licensing options outside the scope of DIRECTED.

3 RIM2D

RIM2D is a high-resolution, two-dimensional hydrodynamic model developed by the Section Hydrology of GFZ (Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences) for fast flood simulations. It is applicable for coastal, pluvial, and fluvial flood modeling, integrating fast numerical techniques leveraging GPU compute capabilities to simulate flood dynamics. Its ability to handle large-scale simulations while maintaining computational efficiency makes it a valuable tool for flood risk assessment, infrastructure planning, climate adaptation strategies, and early-warning and flood impact forecasting systems, helping to mitigate flood impacts and improve disaster preparedness.

3.1 Description

RIM2D is a two-dimensional raster-based hydrodynamic model. It utilizes the local inertia formulation of the shallow water equations (Bates et al., 2010), a widely recognized approach for modelling fluvial floodplain inundation (Apel et al., 2022; Khosh Bin Ghomash et al., 2024). To improve numerical stability under near- and supercritical flow regimes, RIM2D incorporates the diffusion-based stabilization technique introduced by De Almeida et al. (2012), plus an internal algorithm to catch remaining numerical instabilities.

One of RIM2D's key advantages lies in its computational performance. Written in Fortran and optimized for GPU execution using NVIDIA's CUDA Fortran libraries, it enables highly parallelized simulations at a fraction of the cost associated with traditional multi-core CPU clusters. This makes RIM2D a particularly efficient and scalable solution for simulating floods on a large scale, with applications spanning coastal, pluvial, and riverine flood events, as well as early warning systems and flood risk analysis.

3.2 Advancements

As part of DIRECTED Task 2.2, substantial progress has been achieved in improving RIM2D's interoperability, user-friendliness, and computational efficiency, e.g. with a view to

the Data Fabric. Key upgrades include the creation of a dedicated QGIS plugin suite, integration of Google Earth for result visualization, support for NetCDF input and output raster formats, and the addition of river discharge inputs at boundary conditions. Furthermore, the model code has been re-worked for better performance and to support multi-GPU computation for even higher computation speed, enabling also the simulation of larger model domains at higher resolution. These developments significantly boost RIM2D's usability, performance, and interoperability with external modelling tools and platforms.

QGIS Plugin for RIM2D

The development of a QGIS plugin toolkit suite for RIM2D eases the development of RIM2D models considerably. It is designed to support the end-to-end workflow of the model, encompassing input data preparation, model setup, and visualization of simulation results. The plugin is developed as free and open-source software under the GNU General Public License v3.0, enabling users to freely use, modify, and distribute the software while ensuring transparency and reproducibility.

Figure 3: User interfaces of the Model setup (a) and Result Visualizer (b) sections of the plugin in QGIS. Satellite imagery: © Google Earth 2024.

By leveraging QGIS's intuitive graphical interface and powerful geospatial capabilities, the developed plugins make RIM2D more accessible to a broader spectrum of users. [Figure 3](#) illustrates the user interface of two tools included in the QGIS plugin suite. As an open-source platform compatible with major operating systems (e.g., Windows, macOS, and Linux), QGIS enables widespread adoption of RIM2D across diverse user groups. The plugins also enhance the model's interoperability with various geospatial datasets, supporting its integration into broader environmental and infrastructure assessments.

Hydrodynamic modelling requires high-quality input data—such as Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), land use classifications, and Manning's roughness coefficients—prepared in a consistent format. Manually processing these datasets and converting them to the input formats required by RIM2D can be both time-consuming and error-prone. The plugin suite addresses this challenge by providing tools to:

- Transform DEMs into the necessary raster formats while preserving spatial resolution.
- Automate the resampling, re-projection, and masking of DEMs to align with the simulation domain.
- Incorporate land cover data to assign Manning's roughness coefficients, using either pre-set templates or user-customized values.
- Handle additional required or optional inputs for RIM2D, such as building data, surface infiltration rates, initial water levels, urban sewer system details, and more.
- Define a specific model region using a simple polygon.
- Processing the spatially distributed rainfall data for pluvial flood modelling:
 - for synthetic rainfall
 - using rainfall radar data (RADOLAN for Germany): selection of the RADOLAN product and specify the start and end dates for the rainfall data to be downloaded.
- Choose the desired output format accepted by RIM2D, i.e. ASCII (text) or NetCDF files.

The chosen data is subsequently retrieved, processed, and formatted for use in RIM2D. This enhances the efficiency of entering rainfall data into RIM2D in Germany, offering a remarkably fast, effective, and intuitive experience. The plugin has already proven its value by establishing boundary conditions for pluvial flood models in research like Khosh Bin Ghomash et al. (2024b). In addition to its role in RIM2D, the acquired RADOLAN data can be utilized across a range of other domains and models, including agricultural water management, environmental impact assessments, and infrastructure resilience simulations.

Moreover, In the past, setting simulation parameters like boundary conditions, rainfall inputs, and flow characteristics involved manually adjusting configuration files. The QGIS plugins now provide a straightforward graphical interface within QGIS, enabling users to:

- Define boundary conditions (e.g., inflow hydrographs, water levels) using interactive, map-based tools.
- Enter precipitation data sourced from radar or observational records.
- Adjust different simulation settings (e.g. time steps, duration, output format, etc.) directly through drop-down menus.

NetCDF Output Support for Interoperability

To enhance data interoperability, NetCDF support has been added for RIM2D inputs and outputs. Previously, the model only supported ASCII raster files, which limited interoperability with many hydrological and climate models.

By implementing NetCDF outputs, RIM2D can now interface with a wider range of external models and data platforms, increasing its utility in interdisciplinary research and operational flood forecasting. Additionally, the NetCDF compression option reduces data storage requirements considerably.

Support for Discharge as Model Input

RIM2D requires water level as an input boundary condition for rivers in the model, which constrains its flexibility when coupling with hydrological models or being used in study areas where water level data was not available. In DIRECTED, support for discharge inputs has been introduced, allowing users to:

- Directly use river discharge data as a boundary condition.
- Improve integration with rainfall-runoff and hydrological models.
- Enhance simulation accuracy in scenarios where discharge data is more readily available than water level measurements.

The discharge inputs can be converted in the QGIS plugin to water levels for RIM2D. Utilities are provided to calculate the slope at the location of the input, which is required to convert discharge to water levels using Manning's formula. This improvement makes RIM2D more versatile and applicable to a wider range of flood modelling scenarios and also increases its interoperability with other models, particularly in DIRECTED.

Containerization of model code and API

RIM2D has been containerized with all dependencies and the runtime environment in a docker image. This facilitates the execution on (cloud) compute clusters without the need of compiling the code and the dependencies, which typically has to be adapted to each individual compute environment. This considerably eases the use of RIM2D by diverse users in diverse computing environments. Additionally, for running RIM2D from within the Data Fabric an API was developed, sending the docker image with required data for model execution to a cloud computing environment.

Google Earth Integration for Result Validation

Another key advancement is the ability to visualize RIM2D results in Google Earth. This feature enables users to compare simulated flood extents with real-world observations, such as social media posts, satellite imagery, and drone surveys. One of the challenges in flood modelling is validating results with real-time or historical data. By leveraging Google Earth, users can:

- Overlay RIM2D flood maps on high-resolution satellite imagery to visually assess the accuracy of simulations.
- Compare model predictions with georeferenced images and user-generated content, such as flood reports shared on social media.
- Improve stakeholder engagement by presenting results in an accessible and widely used platform.

Summary

The enhancements introduced significantly improve RIM2D's accessibility, interoperability, and computational efficiency. The QGIS plugin simplifies model setup and execution, while Google Earth integration enhances validation workflows. The addition of NetCDF support broadens compatibility with external models, and the ability to use discharge as an input improves hydrological coupling. Finally, multi-GPU support dramatically increases processing power, making RIM2D an easily scalable flood modelling tool. The containerization of RIM2D in a docker container provides an efficient and ready to go package for running the model in an HPC cluster environment without the need for code compilation. These advancements collectively position RIM2D as a cutting-edge solution for flood risk assessment, early warning systems, and climate adaptation planning.

3.3 Accessibility

Code and content:

The code for RIM2D and the plugin are stored and documented in the GitLab instance of GFZ:

- RIM2D : <https://git.gfz-potsdam.de/hydro/rfm/rim2d>
- RIM2D QGIS Plugins: https://git.gfz-potsdam.de/hydro/rfm/rim2d_qplug

Notes: documentations and test cases are included in the repository. RIM2D is open source for scientific use under the EUPL1.2 license. For commercial use license fees apply. The QGIS plugins are open source and accessible under the GNU v3.0 license. Access to the repos is granted upon request (Contact: heiko.apel@gfz.de).

Scientific publications:

- Khosh Bin Ghomash, S., Yeste, P., Apel, H., and Nguyen, V. D.: Monte Carlo-based sensitivity analysis of the RIM2D hydrodynamic model for the 2021 flood event in

western Germany, *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.*, 25, 975–990, <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-25-975-2025>, 2025.

- Khosh Bin Ghomash, S., Apel, H., and Caviedes-Voullième, D.: Are 2D shallow-water solvers fast enough for early flood warning? A comparative assessment on the 2021 Ahr valley flood event, *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.*, 24, 2857–2874, <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-24-2857-2024>, 2024.
- Khosh Bin Ghomash, S., Apel, H., Schröter, K., and Steinhausen, M.: Brief Communication: Rapid high-resolution flood impact-based early warning is possible with RIM2D: a showcase for the 2023 pluvial flood in Braunschweig, *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci. Discuss.* [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-2024-139>, in review, 2024.
- Apel, H., Benisch, J., Helm, B., Vorogushyn, S., & Merz, B. (2024). Fast urban inundation simulation with RIM2D for flood risk assessment and forecasting. *Frontiers in Water*, 6, 1310182. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frwa.2024.1310182>
- Apel, H., Vorogushyn, S., and Merz, B.: Brief communication: Impact forecasting could substantially improve the emergency management of deadly floods: case study July 2021 floods in Germany, *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.*, 22, 3005–3014, <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-3005-2022>, 2022.

4 Danube model

The Danube Model (abbreviated DM; formerly known as *Future Danube Model* and labelled as the *Seamless Forecasting Tool* in the DIRECTED Grant Agreement) is a combined eco-hydrological and hydrodynamics model simulating landscape water fluxes and river discharges including flood stages and runoff velocities. It contains a detailed landscape representation including soil profiles, land use or land cover data considering crop growth dynamics, and subbasin and channel geometries. Calibrated with weather (gridded daily observations) on water stage and river runoff measurements from several gauges it generates detailed maps on flood events (e.g. water depths at 90 m resolution) under climate scenarios.

4.1 Description

The two main components of the DM is the SWIM model, driven by gridded weather or climate scenario data, for distributed runoff generation and the subsequently applied CaMa-Flood for hydrodynamic flood wave modelling.

SWIM was originally developed by Valentina Krysanova at PIK (Krysanova et al. 1998) combining concepts of the models SWAT and MATSALU, the former of the two being well known among the hydrologic community and with significant impact on the further development of SWIM (Krysanova et al. 2005, 2015). Like SWAT, SWIM divides the landscape, typically a river basin, into subbasins which are further divided into hydrotopes, patches with uniform hydrological behaviour determined by soil profile, land cover, elevation, wetland characteristic and optionally more factors. On a daily time step, water fluxes are calculated on hydrotope level. At the end of each time step, runoff contributions are aggregated on subbasin level. There is also a simple river routing scheme in SWIM, it is however deactivated in favour of CaMa-Flood.

CaMa-Flood is a 1-D hydrodynamical model design). It gains much of its power from meticulously maintained global high-resolution raster maps of the world's river systems (Yamazaki et al. 2017, 2019); quasi 2-D capabilities are implemented via bifurcation controls without losing the numerical advantage of 1-D modelling.

However, in the original implementation of the Danube Model, CaMa-Flood was run on the same subbasin map originally provided for SWIM. The DM was first realized in 2019 as the “Future Danube Model (FDM)” in the H2020 INSURANCE project. There were fixed upstream–downstream relationships between the subbasins, and the effect of levees could only be roughly approximated by deepening the parameterized river beds. Downscaling with

high-resolution elevation rasters (ASTER, 25 m) to obtain water depths in floodplains during flood required external postprocessing and delivered mixed results (e.g. visible steps at subbasin boundaries).

4.2 Advancements

The predecessor of the Danube Model, i.e. “Future Danube Model”, was advanced in several respects. In short, improvements and new developments covered:

- Coupling of the runoff generation part (SWIM) to the flood propagation part (CaMa-Flood); the latter no longer depends on geometries and parameters applied in SWIM,
- Flood depth downscaling based on CaMa-Flood code supplements and MERIT elevation data,
- Consideration of man-made flood protection structures (levees) in CaMa-Flood with the ability to simulate and downscale with actual levee line geometries, and realistic setting of levee crown heights based on overtopping return intervals.

While the pre-calibrated SWIM part was kept unchanged in DIRECTED, the most recent version 4.2 of CaMa-Flood containing many new developments and some fundamental changes replaced its predecessor. Sticking with the SWIM subbasin maps in CaMa-Flood – a sub-optimal setup due to missing interconnections aside from river main channels – did however not work with the new code anyway: massive numerical problems emerged for unresolved reasons. CaMa-Flood could be run smoothly using its own geodata – after a new coupling tool transferring the runoff contributions between the different geometries had been implemented. Eventual resampling errors should be over-compensated through the more accurate elevation data of the MERIT-based CaMa-Flood maps and their higher resolution – the average CaMa-Flood unit catchment size is 22 km² while the average SWIM subbasin covers an area of 69 km².

Flood depth downscaling is now also included in CaMa-Flood. It required extra high-resolution (3 arc second) maps over the Danube basin to be obtained personally from the CaMa-Flood inventor and developer Prof. Dai Yamazaki (U Tokyo) – under the limiting condition that no sequence of flood probability maps be produced. (With enough single event maps, which are allowed, probabilities could be calculated in the postprocessing, though.) Anyway, the downscaling products are largely free from artifacts, and a couple of animated flood maps have been produced for Eastern Austria, the Zala County, and the lower Sava River.

From the first downscaling results, a formerly ignored problem could be identified: the missing information on levees sheltering large parts of the floodplains except for very

extreme events (such as the Sava River flood in May 2024). To reproduce the confinement of the streams in the model is also necessary to obtain realistic flood wave diffusion. Building on a levee module in the CaMa-Flood code which had to be explicitly activated, routines to upscale levee lines from their actual locations in the landscape to catchment parameters and downscale the simulated water stages back to high-resolution flood maps have been developed and applied to the lower Sava tributary embedded in extensive riparian wetlands which had been regularly flooded before the construction of levees.

In the original CaMa-Flood supplement, levee heights are estimated through a log function applied to average discharges which is not more than a first guess. Given the heterogeneity of discharge variabilities in the different parts of the river basin, model runs using this setup produced frequent overtopping of levee lines in several places. This problem was tackled by estimating extreme value distributions for flood heights for each unit catchment / river reach from historical time series (re-analyses) produced under the boundary condition of perfect (“sky-high”) levees. This allowed for setting the model levee heights according to prescribed return periods of overtopping or levee failures, the only flood protection metric that has been mapped for Europe so far. However, the respective studies differ a lot over the Danube basin (cf. Figs S1 and S2 in the supplement to Paprotny et al. 2024) and only agree in a gradient to shorter return periods towards the south-east of the basin. Therefore a relatively simple setting had been implemented: 50 years in the north-west, and 25 years in Ukraine, Moldova, Romania, Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, and any country located more towards the south-east.

4.3 Accessibility

Technical documentation:

- SWIM User Manual: https://www.pik-potsdam.de/~wortmann/swim/swim_manual.pdf

(Although last updated in 2022, some parts of this manual are outdated.)

- The CaMa-Flood User Manual is available for registered users from the CaMa-Flood website: <http://hydro.iis.u-tokyo.ac.jp/~yamadai/cama-flood/>

Code and content:

- The SWIM code is not ready for publication (see under “Availability” below)
- The CaMa-Flood code can be obtained through the CaMa-Flood website after registration: <http://hydro.iis.u-tokyo.ac.jp/~yamadai/cama-flood/>

- Some high-resolution maps used for downscaling of CaMa-Flood results can only be obtained directly from the developer, Prof. Dai Yamazaki (U Tokyo), together with a personal user license whose conditions have to be negotiated individually.

Scientific publications:

- Krysanova et al. 1998, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3800\(97\)00204-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3800(97)00204-4)
- Krysanova et al. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.5619>
- Krysanova et al. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02626667.2014.925560>
- Yamazaki et al. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010WR009726>
- Yamazaki et al. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2012WR011869>
- Yamazaki et al. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1002/wrcr.20552>
- Yamazaki et al. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GL072874>
- Yamazaki et al. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019WR024873>
- Paprotny et al. 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-024-07039-5>
- A new publication about flood scenarios simulated by the DM is planned to be submitted in December 2025 for an upcoming ISIMIP special issue.

Availability:

- SWIM is © Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research. Due to a large diaspora of former developers contributing to the model code whose signatures would be required to greenlight a public license, a future open source distribution of SWIM is improbable. As a similar, publicly available and well-known alternative we recommend SWAT, originally developed and maintained at A&T University, Temple, TX: <https://swat.tamu.edu>.
- For the CaMa-Flood materials two licenses and a special regulation apply: The codes for hydrodynamic calculation are distributed under [Apache 2.0 license](#). The basic river maps (without 3sec & 15sec data) have got the [CC-BY 4.0 license](#). The advanced river map (with 3sec data) needed for high-resolution downscaling are however only shared on request (with a special agreement depending on the purpose of use). The latter was obtained for the Danube Basin map and exclusively for usage within DIRECTED.

5 Damage Cost

The Damage Cost model (in Danish: [OS2-Skadesøkonomi](#)) provides a methodological and modelling framework to support comprehensive and multi-sectoral economic damage assessments of flooding on land from pluvial, coastal, and riverine sources. The model rests on open geographical data and assumes the availability of detailed flood hazard maps. Depth-damage functions for multiple economic sectors are included, which can be supplemented by socioeconomic data on people in risk areas. From a socioeconomic perspective the model assesses the risk of flooding as a basis for decision-making on adaptation strategies.

5.1 Description

The current version of the Damage Cost model supports damage cost assessments across ten different socioeconomic sectors at very high resolution. To identify assets that are affected by a flood from either coastal, pluvial or riverine sources the model carries out a spatial overlay analysis combining sector-specific data with flood hazard maps provided by the user. For applications in Denmark, the modelling suite includes a set of state-of-the-art flood hazard maps, e.g. adequate for representing urban scales. For six of the ten sectors (buildings, roads and traffic, humans and health, tourism, recreational areas and agriculture), the Damage Cost model estimates losses due to flooding in monetary values, whereas for the last four sectors (critical infrastructure, industry, public service and ecosystems) exposed features are highlighted using indicators. For the six sectors, where a monetary loss is estimated, depth-damage curves have been developed based on national data for Denmark, including insurance payouts related to coastal and pluvial floods, standardized cost values provided by the national authorities in Denmark (e.g. direct economic costs related to loss of working ability, extended travel time, etc.) or derived from recent scientific publications.

The current version of the Damage Cost model is developed as an open-source plugin with QGIS open-source software. The embedded depth-damage functions comprise a set of SQL commands to combine the input data with auxiliary data tables that are installed together with the plugin. To optimize the speed and stability of the computations and the data processing, all calculations are carried out within a PostgreSQL database. QGIS is only used to run the models and to view the results. In this way, Damage Cost offers a flexible and modular framework, where both sector-specific data and flood maps can easily be updated by local users and non-experts to adhere to national or local standards or to take advantage of access to accurate and site-specific municipal data. This design makes it easy to customize the model to different locations and situations; while ensuring it is based on the

best available data to stay relevant and accurate even in very specific local and urban contexts.

5.2 Advancements

Over the course of the DIRECTED project, the Damage Cost model was advanced in different ways to facilitate its direct use by stakeholders as well as its interoperability with different flood models and CLIMADA (see below).

- The original version of the Damage Cost model was developed for ESRI's commercial ArcGIS software. Aiming to support non-experts, in the early stages of DIRECTED, the original model code was ported to QGIS, which is free software, and rewritten for optimization as discussed above. The input interface was improved to allow the Damage Cost model to be able to import GIS-flood maps from different sources, e.g. RIM2D, and SaferPlaces. Likewise, the user interface was improved significantly to accommodate ease-of-use by municipalities and practitioners.
- To facilitate complementary use along workflows of varying complexity, the damage cost curves developed for Damage Cost based on public and private Danish data were ported to CLIMADA. While the current version of Damage Cost, i.e. [OS2-Skadesøkonomi](#), has been tailored for non-academic use, this comes with the loss of flexibility. Effectively combining the two models, ensures that the local and validated economic knowledge behind Damage Cost is merged with the flexibility of CLIMADA.

Finally, Damage Cost was integrated into the RWL1 Data Fabric to demonstrate knowledge and data interoperability. A large data set, combining scenarios and authoritative climate projections from the Danish Meteorological Institute with associated flood simulations using RIM2D, SaferPlaces and a third reference flood model (SCALGO Live), was produced and analysed using Damage Cost; these results are used to populate the RWL1 Data Fabric for real-life demonstration and evaluation of work flows and value added.

5.3 Accessibility

Technical documentation:

- <https://github.com/Skadesokonomi/Dokumentation-og-vejledninger> (mostly in Danish)

Code and content:

- GitHub repository: <https://github.com/Skadesokonomi>
- The GitHub repository contains demo data and examples of use within the technical documentation (mostly in Danish)

Scientific publications:

- Halsnæs, K., Veng, E., Kaspersen, P. S., Mik-Meyer, V., Sunding, T.P., and Drews, M. (2025). Measuring the social impacts of coastal flooding: A Danish example. In review in Climatic Change.
- Kaspersen, P.S., Veng, E., Some, S., Drews, M., and Halsnæs, K. (2025). An Open Source Spatial DamageCost Model for Assessment of the Socioeconomic Impacts of Flooding to Support Decision-making on Climate Change Adaptation. In review in Climate Services.
- Halsnæs, K., Larsen, M. A. D., Sunding, T. P., & Dømggaard, M. L. (2023). The value of advanced flood models, damage costs and land use data in cost-effective climate change adaptation. Climate Services, 32, Article 100424.

Availability:

Damage Cost is open source and available for everyone to download and use. In general, the code is based on open data sources, although in a few cases access to the underlying economic data used for calibrating the embedded depth-damage curves are restricted. This applies to the original insurance data used for estimating the depth-damage curves related to buildings, and to data sources used for inferring the depth-damage curves for human health. Both are restricted due to GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) rules. The data used to calculate indicators related to critical infrastructure is restricted for security reasons.

Originally developed by the Division of Climate and Energy Policy, Technical University of Denmark (DTU), the code is now maintained and made available by the OS2 Community in Denmark, which is an association of Danish municipalities, academic and commercial developers offering user-friendly open-source tools to Danish municipalities and other professional users. The code is widely used by Danish public authorities, municipalities, and engineering companies in Denmark. Ongoing methodological developments are carried out at the Technical University of Denmark in the context of EU and national projects (e.g. DIRECTED) and eventually integrated into the stable version of the model. Training and advice is regularly offered to professional users by members of the OS2 working group on Damage Cost, and the model is used for teaching at the Technical University of Denmark.

6 CLIMADA

[CLIMADA](#) (Aznar-Siguan and Bresch, 2019) is an open-source probabilistic natural catastrophe and climate change adaptation model which can also calculate the potentially averted damages due to implemented adaptation measures (including infrastructural and behavioral changes). It integrates hazard, exposure and vulnerability data, providing multi-hazard assessments across flexible geographical and temporal scales.

6.1 Description

CLIMADA provides a framework for users to combine exposure, hazard and vulnerability or impact data to calculate risk. Users can create probabilistic impact data from event sets, look at how climate change affects these impacts, and see how adaptation measures can effectively change them. CLIMADA also allows for studies of individual events, historical event sets and forecasts.

The model is highly customizable, meaning that users can work with out-of-the-box data provided for different hazards, population and economic exposure, or can provide their own data for part or all of the analysis. The pre-packaged data make CLIMADA particularly useful for users who focus on just one element of risk, since CLIMADA can ‘fill in the gaps’ for hazard, exposure or vulnerability in the rest of the analysis.

The model core is designed to give as much flexibility as possible when describing the elements of risk, meaning that CLIMADA isn’t limited to particular hazards, exposure types or impacts.

CLIMADA is written in Python and provides classes, methods and data for exposure, hazard and impact functions (also called vulnerability functions), plus a financial model and a framework to analyze adaptation measures. Additional classes and data for common uses, such as economic exposures or tropical storms and tutorials for every class are available.

In addition, the framework supports a diverse range of input data and includes tailored solutions for integrating these from specific sources (including OpenStreetMap, Copernicus Climate Data Store, ISIMIP, CMIP, and more).

6.2 Advancements

Within DIRECTED's Work Package 2, CLIMADA saw two major releases of its source code, (from version 4.0 to now 6.0). These releases included several **minor improvements** to facilitate its use (including file reading and writing functions, utility functions, and performance), **complete overhauls** of two of its core classes (used to represent exposure layers), as well as its documentation website. These recent developments also include the addition of multiple **major new features**, extending CLIMADA with new tools useful for interoperability (open-street map data handling, impact function calibration, uncertainty and sensitivity of analysis to climate change tool).

New developments during DIRECTED

CLIMADA follows a continuous process of development, both for maintenance and the development of new features. Although the following features were already planned outside DIRECTED, their design and implementation were nourished by the co-creation process of the different RWLs.

CLIMADA relies on the use of impact functions to compute how assets or people are affected by hazards. These functions are rarely known and must most of the time be calibrated (for instance using past events). This calibration can be difficult for non-expert users of CLIMADA, although it is essential to conduct meaningful evaluation of risk. In the optic of facilitating the process for non-expert users (be it DIRECTED modelers or end-users), a calibration module was developed and published ([Riedel et al., \(2024\)](#)). This module and its documentation enable CLIMADA users to calibrate impact function using hazard, exposure, and impact data from past events using established calibration techniques like Bayesian optimization.

As the use of open street map data to define exposure layers is becoming more and more common, we added a full tutorial on leveraging the OSM-flex package within CLIMADA to easily download, parse and use OSM data for that purpose.

A function was added to the uncertainty module, to allow the uncertainty and sensitivity analysis of impact change calculations. A described example can be found in the [module description](#).

Overhauls for better interoperability of CLIMADA

The Centroids and Exposures classes received a complete overhaul, to now rely on the GeoPandas package. In addition to simplifying and improving the efficiency of the source code, these changes will facilitate the imports and exports of exposure layers, leveraging the multiple standard readers and writers of GeoPandas.

In addition, the documentation website of CLIMADA was also completely redesigned to account for its growing complexity and improves its clarity. Although the definitive version will be released with the next major release of CLIMADA, it is already available at the following address: <https://climada-python.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.

This overhaul improves the general structure of the website to better distinguish information for users and for developers, improving the accessibility to new users.

Interoperability sandbox examples

In parallel to these improvements, several Jupyter notebooks have been written to demonstrate possible dataflows using CLIMADA in conjunction with other tools from the DIRECTED project. All these notebooks are available in [the interoperability sandbox](#). These notebooks can serve as a guide for constructing the API to the Data Fabric and demonstrate how different tools can be coupled to support CCA and DRM. We give a brief overview of these notebooks below.

Utilization of flood data generated by the Danube Model

This example showcases how CLIMADA can be used to load flood hazard data generated from the Danube model to conduct an impact assessment. Users who can use the Danube Model from PIK can load the produced netCDF files as a Hazard object in CLIMADA and compute the corresponding impact assessments, with exposure of their choice (the internal CLIMADA LitPop in the example).

Figure 4: Example of Exposure data from the LitPop module of CLIMADA. The figure depicts local monetary value (log10 scale) in a broad region around the Danube Region, values are estimated based on population density and night light activity.

Figure 5: Example of Hazard data loaded from the Danube model into CLIMADA. The figure depicts maximum river flood height (intensity [m]) in the Danube basin for all events considered (flood depths for each day between 1971 and 2023).

Figure 6: Example of resulting impact evaluation in RWL Danube region using CLIMADA. Values represent the average annual impact given previously shown exposure and hazard.

Integration of flood event data from SafePlaces and RIM2D

Likewise, two other notebooks showcase how CLIMADA can be used to load hazard data from the **SaferPlaces** or **RIM2D** models. Considering the high resolution of the data for both sources, two approaches are presented and compared in the notebook:

- An approach which coarsens the resolution of the data to enable faster computation at the cost of precision loss
- An approach loading the full resolution of the data at the cost of higher computation requirements

Figure 7: Example of resulting impact assessment for RWL Emilia Romagna.

The second part of the notebook presents how to compute the cost-benefit analysis of measures that were included in the **SaferPlaces** simulation.

Application of Social Vulnerability Index (SVI) data

Another example showcases how the Social Vulnerability Index data can be loaded and included in the exposure data. This inclusion can easily be achieved via a spatial matching, leveraging GeoPandas. This can be used in impact assessments to distinguish total impacts per vulnerability group and help design measures that account for the vulnerability of the affected population.

Average Annual Share of People in Each Vulnerability Group Impacted by Hazard (> 30 m/s)

Figure 8 Example of obtainable result - Share and absolute number of people affected in each vulnerability group by hazards above a certain intensity.

Risk transfer mechanisms for portfolios or individual assets

This example demonstrates how existing mechanisms within CLIMADA can be used to include risk transfer measures by applying both insurance cover and deductible to either a portfolio or individual assets, using **SaferPlaces** flood data and the **building exposure data** available for Vienna.

Soon to be released advancements

In addition to these examples, several ongoing developments for CLIMADA aim to enhance its interoperability with other tools, models, and frameworks. Although these developments are not yet present in CLIMADA stable version (6.0), access to these new features can be granted upon request:

- Ongoing work to facilitate the use of impact functions from the DTU model within CLIMADA.
- Development of a new module to conduct impact assessments that include risk trajectories, capturing the evolution of risk between two time points by accounting for changes in Exposure, Hazard, and Vulnerability.

- A significant revamp of the “cost benefit” module into an “option appraisal” module to leverage the new risk trajectories capabilities, enabling the evaluation and comparison of different adaptation plans, and allowing the integration of high-resolution social data such as the Social Vulnerability Index (SVI). This will consider implementation timings, costs, and potential benefits over time of the considered measures.
- Improvements to the adaptation measure module to simplify its use, and align it to the new option appraisal module.
- Development of a new module to perform MCDM, complementing the option appraisal module by including non-monetary criteria (such as gender, age, livelihoods, approval, etc.) in addition to the traditional cost-benefit approach.

6.3 Accessibility

Technical documentation:

- [Link to user guides and technical documentation](#)

Code and content:

- [GitHub repository](#)
- Demos are available in tutorials / user-guides in the documentation website

Scientific publications:

- All publications made using CLIMADA are referred [here](#) and their code [here](#).
- Aznar-Siguan, G. and Bresch, D. N., 2019: CLIMADA v1: a global weather and climate risk assessment platform, Geosci. Model Dev., <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-3085-2019>
- Bresch, D. N. and Aznar-Siguan, G., 2021: CLIMADA v1.4.1: Towards a globally consistent adaptation options appraisal tool, Geosci. Model Dev., <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-2020-151>
- Riedel et al. (2024). A Module for Calibrating Impact Functions in the Climate Risk Modeling Platform CLIMADA. Journal of Open Source Software, 9(99), 6755. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.06755>.

- Evelyn Mühlhofer et al. (2024). OpenStreetMap for multi-faceted climate risk assessments. Environ. Res. Commun., 6, 015005
<https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7620/ad15ab>

Availability:

CLIMADA is fully open-source and available for anyone to use, modify, and distribute under the terms of the GNU General Public License v3. CLIMADA is written in Python and designed with both usability and flexibility in mind. The extensive documentation and tutorials ensure easy use of the software. Furthermore, CLIMADA has a growing community of users and contributors. Several different channels (notably the GitHub repository, the mailing list, the monthly calls and the yearly “CLIMADA days”) allow users to share their insights, receive support for their applications, as well as develop new modules, or collaborate on projects.

7 Climate Connectivity Hub and Taxonomy

The Climate Connectivity Hub is a search and discovery tool that helps users access relevant knowledge and identify organizations working on climate, disaster risk and mitigation. It also serves as a way to test AI and machine learning methods to generate actionable insights for policy, research, and practice. By linking fragmented content in climate knowledge that is shared online, the Hub quickly reveals connections, breaks down disciplinary silos, and fosters shared understanding, ultimately accelerating learning and the scaling of climate action.

Figure 9: Content from multiple online platforms connected by keywords (orange nodes), projects (blue nodes) and organizations (implementing entities).

7.1 Description

The Climate Connectivity Hub improves the discoverability and integration of existing information by sourcing data from various platforms and connecting it with tags (keywords that different platforms use to describe content). This approach enhances the interoperability of knowledge online. It is intended for researchers, technical planners and practitioners

working on the topic of climate change generally and is particularly being tested with climate change adaptation or disaster risk management stakeholders. Additionally, the Hub is driven by a taxonomy which further strengthens these connections by linking dispersed knowledge on topics like climate change adaptation, disaster risk reduction, and related areas (e.g., from other platforms and databases such as CORDIS). This interconnected knowledge is more accessible to diverse audiences, promoting cross-fertilization among actors who may encounter new and previously undiscovered platforms. The Hub includes content from weADAPT, CORDIS (currently Horizon Europe Cluster 5, Destination 1 data), and other platforms such as UNDRR's PreventionWeb, the Resilience Platform, and Climate-ADAPT.

7.2 Advancements

Content in the Hub has been made more interoperable by:

- Identifying and surfacing emerging shared vocabularies from DIRECTED and other project outcomes to strengthen alignment across research, policy, and practice.
- Mapping organisations by topic to uncover collaboration patterns, highlight knowledge gaps, and foster cross-disciplinary connections.

Together, these efforts create a dynamic and robust approach that significantly enhances information interoperability.

The IPCC glossary and UNDRR taxonomy, considered the most robust sources of definitions in the fields of climate change and disasters respectively, were imported as seed taxonomies. This means they serve as the basis for the taxonomy using the following steps.

Figure 10: Curation of the Climate Connectivity Taxonomy and its integration into the Climate Connectivity Hub (Source: Bharwani et al., forthcoming).

The taxonomy that drives the Hub is open and accessible for use by other platforms, websites and tools. Updates to the tool have been documented in a paper currently under review.

Figure 11: Implementation of the taxonomy in the Hub.

Next steps will involve incorporating new taxonomies, testing them with stakeholders in different contexts (e.g. in the Directed Real World Labs), and making the updated taxonomy available for use on platforms in a glossary format, such as on the MAIA project website, and on partner websites like the Climate EU Mitigation Portal, the weADAPT platform, the Agora Community Hub and the Directed project’s Data Fabric.

Within the DIRECTED Data Fabric, a first prototypical implementation has been developed to showcase how the taxonomy from the Hub can be used to support end-users in understanding the content, and context, of data and model outputs. This has been established with keywords, accessed via the Hub’s current keyword by name API prototype. Users can click on hyperlinks within the Data Fabric where more in-depth terminology is needed, with the term then being displayed in a dialogue box within the Data Fabric. At the bottom of the dialogue, there is a link that takes the user to the Hub’s search interface. Further developments and integration of the Hub are to be determined in the next coming months. For example, definitions, metadata and scope notes for Data Fabric-specific terms will be co-developed with RWL hosts and stakeholders.

Figure 12: Integration of the taxonomy in the DIRECTED Data Fabric.

7.3 Accessibility

Technical documentation for the taxonomy:

- The current *prototype* API can be accessed here: <http://connectivity-hub.com/>

Code and content:

- Climate Connectivity Hub: <https://connectivity-hub.weadapt.org/>
- Tutorial video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xozHPfzDPfo&t=304s>

Scientific publications:

- "Scaling and accelerating knowledge interoperability for climate action through the Climate Connectivity Hub and Taxonomy" (*forthcoming*) in Climatic Change journal MAIA special issue on climate adaptation knowledge management: <https://maia-project.eu/knowledge-base/springer-nature-climatic-change-journal-special-issue/>

Availability:

- The Climate Connectivity Hub and Taxonomy are currently live and subject to ongoing improvements based on feedback being gathered through a survey (<https://forms.office.com/e/JsTK4j9acq>) and from the Directed RWLs.

8 Citizen VR App

In the original DIRECTED proposal Oasis Hub included the potential of adapting the Citizen App from the tool Oasis-CAIMAN. The Oasis-CAIMAN citizen app collects damage information from citizens after an extreme event. However, during the course of discussions with Real World Labs it was decided that App's are often not widely used by citizens. Instead, through the RiskTandem Framework discussions stakeholders felt that providing flood safety information would be a better solution to communications with citizen safety training. Thus, Oasis Hub requested an amendment change, which was accepted, to develop Immersive training, initially a Flood Safety Application/ Experience.

8.1 Description

The Emilia-Romagna Flood Safety VR App was developed using the Unity game engine to provide an interactive, simulation-based environment for citizen flood preparedness. The development process followed an iterative design cycle combining SaferPlaces visualisation data, user-experience prototyping, and performance optimisation for VR deployment. The tool was developed using flood safety information from ARSTPC-ER.

8.2 Advancements

Because of the changes requested by the Real World Labs, the Immersive App was developed from scratch. Advancement therefore represents the full build of the App as follows:

Development Environment

- Engine: Unity 2022 LTS, selected for its cross-platform VR support and extensibility.
- **Hardware:** Optimised for standalone VR headsets (e.g. Meta Quest 2/3) with scalable options for desktop VR.
Languages/Frameworks: Core functionality developed in C#; Unity XR Interaction Toolkit used for immersive interaction handling.

Data Integration and Scenario Modelling

- **Flood Visualisation Data:** Hydrodynamic modelling outputs from SaferPlaces were imported into Unity as visualisation layers to represent inundation extent and depth in live conditions during a flood.
- **Environment Design:** A stylised but data-informed 3D representation of the Emilia-Romagna landscape was constructed, integrating terrain meshes and built environment features to situate users in recognisable contexts.
- **Safety Guidance:** Behavioural instructions (pre-flood, during flood, post-flood) were encoded as in-scene interactions, ensuring direct linkage between environmental cues and user decision points.

Immersive Interaction Design

- **User Navigation:** Teleportation and guided movement systems allowed users to move through affected environments without inducing motion sickness.
- **Scenario Triggers:** Interactive sequences (e.g., turning off power, moving upstairs responding to rising water levels) were implemented.
- **Feedback Mechanisms:** Visual prompts, audio narration, and haptic feedback were integrated to reinforce correct actions and highlight risks.

Testing and Optimisation

- **Prototype Evaluation:** Early builds were tested with local stakeholders and Real World Lab participants to refine usability and cultural relevance.
- **Accessibility:** Text and narration were included in both Italian and English; interface design followed clear-layout principles to accommodate diverse user groups.

Deployment and Replicability

The final build was packaged for sideloading on VR headsets, with options for local installation in municipal training centres, and emergency management workshops. The workflow developed in Unity is replicable, allowing future adaptations for other hazards (e.g., wildfire, urban heat) and other European regions through substitution of local hazard datasets and safety protocols.

8.3 Accessibility

Technical documentation

- User and installation manual: *In preparation; draft version available on request from Oasis Hub.*
- Technical documentation (Unity development workflow, SaferPlaces data integration, and scenario design): *Internal project documentation*

Code and content

- Project repository: Private Unity project repository maintained by Oasis Hub; not publicly accessible.

Download site: Compiled VR app build available for sideloading on request by project partners and Real World Lab demonstrations.

Demo: Public demonstration video released on the DIRECTED YouTube Channel: [\[https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qO1CKM1tEhk\]](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qO1CKM1tEhk).

Scientific publications/Dissemination

- Dissemination: Demonstrations at ECCA 2025 and REMTECH 2025.

Availability

The Emilia-Romagna Flood Safety VR App has been made freely available to ARSTPC-ER (Agenzia Regionale per la Sicurezza Territoriale e la Protezione Civile – Emilia Romagna). In addition to using the VR application, ARSTPC-ER has also been provided with a video of the experience. It is the intention that ARSTPC-ER will integrate this material into their website to support existing written guidance for citizens.

The codebase and Unity project assets remain proprietary to Oasis Hub. Public access is made available via YouTube demo video, with wider deployment subject to specific licensing agreements for educational, municipal, or research purposes.

9 ABSOLUT

ABSOLUT, developed by Tobias Conradt at PIK, is a statistically-based model analyzing the cause-relationship between weather features and annual yields on a regional per-crop basis. Calibrated by historical weather and yield time series it is able to produce yield scenarios under climate change from respective climate scenario data. For DIRECTED, it is applied both on 400 German districts and on more than 200 European NUTS-2 regions to deliver respective scenarios for RWL4, the Rhine-Erft region, and the Zala County in RWL3.

9.1 Description

A detailed description of ABSOLUT including links to the source code and example data on Zenodo is given by Conradt (2022).

The model estimates regional yield values by multiple linear regressions of local weather features temporally aggregated from within the twelve months preceding harvest. While multiple linear regressions per se are a well-established method in yield prediction, the choice of relevant weather features had rarely been optimized before. A common problem given the abundance of possible weather features (meteorological variables times different aggregation periods) is overfitting – the ABSOLUT algorithm circumvents this by also considering the results from other sub-regions within the modelling domain.

The performance depends i.a. on input data quality and varies between crop and region. German national silage maize yields can be predicted solely from weather data until end of August with about the same accuracy as the JRC forecasts in their September MARS bulletins

(https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/monitoring-agricultural-resources-mars/jrc-mars-bulletin_en). Consequently, the pure weather impacts are isolated in yield scenarios under climate change; possible mitigating effects by management (e.g. irrigation) or future CO₂ fertilization are not considered.

9.2 Advancements

The ABSOLUT crop yield model was originally not intended to be applied in DIRECTED, however it appeared that droughts are among the climate change hazards to be considered, and crop yields are strongly affected by drought.

Utilizing the model for the Danube basin (RWL 3) required the first pan-European application of ABSOLUT; it had only been run on district level in some national or regional applications before. A major effort for this application was collecting the historical yield data of numerous crops necessary for calibration from all NUTS-2 regions since the year 2000: Albeit there a respective table does exist in the Eurostat data base it contains lots of gaps, and missing or erroneous entries in former years are never updated despite available data and revisions from national statistical authorities (personal communication with Eurostat staff in 2024)! Consequently, this required a roundtrip through two dozen national statistical web portals, partly not available in English, to obtain sufficiently complete and better maintained data, and a considerable effort for homogenization.

The ABSOLUT code was improved regarding the handling of unique regional IDs (here: NUTS codes) and missing data in input time series; the probability of errors encountered during runtime was reduced at large by adding several error-catching routines.

9.3 Accessibility

Technical documentation:

- Included with the code in the repository, see below

Code and content:

- <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4468608>
- At the time of writing, the most recent version published here was still v1.2. Since then it should have been updated to include the further development under DIRECTED.

Scientific publications:

- Conradt, T. Choosing multiple linear regressions for weather-based crop yield prediction with ABSOLUT v1.2 applied to the districts of Germany. *Int J Biometeorol* 66, 2287–2300 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-022-02356-5>

Availability:

ABSOLUT is © Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research, but nevertheless free software under the GNU General Public License 3, see <https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0>.

10 Social Vulnerability Index

The Social Vulnerability Index (SVI) tool maps at regional and local scales the distribution of social vulnerability to environmental hazards including flooding and heat stress. This index has been developed by University College Cork (UCC) within the [REACHOUT project](#) and is available for application in DIRECTED RWLs. The SVI was not formally part of the DIRECTED project. However, to bridge a gap in the available models around social vulnerability, synergies were captured with the REACHOUT project.

10.1 Description

This index uses information collected through the most recent census. To integrate the various aspects of social vulnerability, a hierarchy of data is used, starting with indicators, which are the factors that influence social vulnerability. These indicators are then grouped to form domains related to a particular category, such as age or income. And finally, these domains are collated into the three main dimensions of social vulnerability: sensitivity, adaptive capacity and enhanced exposure. The dimensions are combined to form the overall vulnerability index.

10.2 Advancements

There is a code created for each specific case study, using 'R' and combining census local information with Copernicus data. The easiest way to run the code is via a Conda environment. Currently, UCC is running the code when census data is made available by specific RWLs. However, details on how to run the code are available in the [SVI handbook](#).

The SVI was applied for the Emilia-Romagna RWL using available Italian Census data (2021). The SVI was visualised as a GIS layer and map and can be integrated in the Data Fabric and/or SaferPlaces platforms. During side-event at the European Climate Adaptation Conference June, 2025, the map (see Figure 13) was used to support discussion with civil protection actors (regional and local level) and researchers around decision-making, resource allocation during past and future coastal and pluvial extreme climate events. The discussions highlighted that integration municipal level social data e.g. disability data would support in improving the index for decision-making. An SVI is also developed for the

Comacchio and Mesola municipal regions but has not yet been used as part of the workshops.

In the Rhine-Erft, there was interest in applying the index but data at the appropriate scale was not available. In Denmark, a social vulnerability index already exists (Prall et al. 2024) and the index is openly available, and has been integrated into the Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) module for the Capital Region of Denmark RWL activities.

Figure 13: Social Vulnerability Index for Rimini (used during interactive ECCA side-event, June 2025) showing the extremely high, very high, relatively high indexes. This was used alongside visualisations from the SafePlaces model for coastal and pluvial flooding

The SVI does not have planned improvements via DIRECTED, rather a focus on broadening its application to support decision-making resource allocation and the prioritisation of action, among civil protection actors, whilst helping to bridge dialogue between civil protection and long-term planning/ climate adaptation.

10.3 Accessibility

Technical documentation:

- The Social Vulnerability Index (SVI) Tool Handbook is available here:
<https://ucc-climpadap.github.io/SVIBook/index.html>

Code and content:

- The SVI code is provided separately for each case study in open GitHub repositories:
 - Cork, Ireland (flooding):
<https://ucc-climpadap.github.io/SVIBook/Cities/Cork.html>
 - Milan, Italy (extreme heat)
<https://ucc-climpadap.github.io/SVIBook/Cities/Milan.html>
 - Logrono, Spain (extreme heat)
<https://ucc-climpadap.github.io/SVIBook/Cities/Logrono.html>

Scientific publications:

- McCullagh, D., Cámara-García, W., Dunne, D., Nowbakht, P., Cumiskey, L., Gannon, C., & Phillips, C. (2025). Development of a Social Vulnerability Index: Enhancing approaches to support climate justice. *MethodsX*, 103290.
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Availability:

To ensure widespread accessibility, all material can be reproduced using the open-sourced code and data.

All code and data from each of the three case studies in the REACHOUT project (Cork, Logroño, Milan) are available to users. As the case studies in Rimini (and possibly other DIRECTED Real World Labs) are further developed, these inputs and outputs will also be included in the open repository.

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(<https://www.forestvalley.org/article/safer-places-innovating-flood-risk-management-for-a-resilient-future>)
Overview: An interview discussing how SaferPlaces supports municipalities, multiutilities, insurance, and finance sectors in flood risk management.
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Annex 1: SaferPlaces

SaferPlaces API Documentation

Since SaferPlaces is a commercially-licensed model, and thereby access to the source code is restricted, a detailed technical description of the API is included below.

Non-Technical Intro

The SaferPlaces API is like a special online tool built using a framework called PygeoAPI. It operates on a cloud computing platform called AWS. This tool is used to handle requests for rainfall simulations and run them efficiently.

How it works:

- **SaferRainProcessor:** This is a key part of the system. It's a piece of software that takes information like elevation data (how high or low the ground is) and rainfall data. It then calculates how deep water would be in different areas.
- **Online Requests:** You can send requests to this tool over the internet. When you do, the SaferRainProcessor starts a job to perform the simulation.
- **Scalability and Reliability:** Because it uses AWS, the system can handle many requests at once and is very reliable, meaning it's less likely to break down.
- **Outputs:** After the simulation, the system provides results, like maps showing water depth.
- **Example Usage:** The document also provides an example of how to send a request to the system to get a simulation done.
- **AWS Serverless Operations:** This part explains how the system uses AWS to manage its resources, like how much computer power or memory it needs, and how it retrieves results from cloud storage.

Think of it as a smart online calculator for rainfall impact. You give it the input (like rain data and terrain information), and it quickly calculates and gives you the output (like a water depth map), using powerful cloud computers to do the work efficiently and reliably.

Audience and prerequisites

This appendix targets technical readers and IT experts. It assumes working knowledge of RESTful APIs and JSON, containerized workloads on AWS (ECS, Batch, Lambda), Python development with PygeoAPI processors, and basic geospatial data concepts (e.g., DEMs,

GeoTIFF outputs). Terminology is intentionally precise and not overly simplified; definitions are provided only where essential.

Overview

This section introduces the SaferPlaces API built on PygeoAPI and deployed on AWS ECS. It explains how processing services are exposed as REST endpoints and executed on AWS Batch or AWS Lambda to provide scalability and reliability. It then details the SaferRainProcessor class, which extends PygeoAPI's BaseProcessor, including its metadata, supported job-control options, and how it binds a rainfall-impact simulation to a callable HTTP process. The execute function is described with its full input contract (DEM, rain, output location, authentication, runtime options), validation steps, and the end-to-end execution flow from parameter parsing to remote job submission and response formatting. The output schema and MIME type are specified, along with a runnable Example Usage (curl POST to /processes/safer-rain-process/execution) that shows the expected request body and typical response. Finally, AWS Serverless Operations summarizes execution modes (sync/async), resource configuration (RAM, vCPU, timeout, retries), and options such as presigned URL generation for retrieving results from cloud storage.

Use this overview as a roadmap to the section; it frames the architecture and execution pattern that the following subsections detail (Class, Function execute, Outputs, Example Usage, and AWS Serverless Operations).

The SaferPlaces API is built on PygeoAPI and runs on AWS ECS infrastructure. PygeoAPI was chosen for its modular design, making it easier to develop new processes and features. Meanwhile, AWS services like ECS, Batch, and Lambda ensure scalability and reliability.

- The SaferRainProcessor is a Python class that extends PygeoAPI's BaseProcessor to provide a processing service for safer rain simulations. It integrates with AWS Batch or AWS Lambda to execute remote computing jobs for analyzing digital elevation models (DEM) with rainfall data to predict water depth output maps.
- PygeoAPI, using BaseProcessor, provides a REST API interface to trigger the process via a POST request to a specific endpoint (e.g. /processes/safer-rain-process/execution). This request executes the execute function with the parameters provided in the request body.

Below is documented Safer Rain PygeoAPI process implementation.

Class: SaferRainProcessor

Initialization

```
SaferRainProcessor(processor_def)
```

Parameters:

- `processor_def` (*dict*): The processor definition provided by the API framework.

Returns:

- An instance of `SaferRainProcessor`.

Metadata

The processor provides metadata about its version, available inputs, outputs, and supported job control options:

- **Version:** 0.2.0
- **ID:** safer-process
- **Job Control Options:** sync-execute, async-execute
- **Keywords:** safer process

Function: execute

```
def execute (self, data)
```

Description

The `execute` function processes input parameters, validates user credentials, constructs an execution event, and triggers an AWS Batch job for processing rainfall simulations.

Inputs

The function accepts a dictionary data with the following keys:

Parameter	Type	Description
Dem	<i>string</i>	Path to the digital elevation model file.
Rain	<i>integer</i>	Volume of rainfall.
Water	<i>string</i>	Path to the water depth output file.
Debug	<i>boolean</i>	Enable debugging mode (default: False).
Image	<i>string</i>	Name of the container image (default: 'safer_rain').

Mode	<i>string</i>	Execution mode (default: 'batch').
Ram	<i>integer</i>	RAM allocation in MB (default: 16384).
Vcpu	<i>float</i>	Number of virtual CPUs (default: 2.0).
Timeout	<i>integer</i>	Job timeout in seconds (default: 600).
Retries	<i>integer</i>	Number of retry attempts (default: 1).
presigned_url_out	<i>boolean</i>	Generate a presigned URL for the output file (default: False).
Sync	<i>boolean</i>	Run the job synchronously (default: False).
User	<i>string</i>	API user for authentication.
Token	<i>string</i>	API token for authentication.

Execution Flow

1. **Extract Input Parameters:** The function retrieves all relevant input parameters, applying default values where necessary.
2. **Validate User Credentials:** Calls `check_credentials(user, token)` to ensure the user is authorized.
3. **Log and Prepare Execution Event:** Constructs an event dictionary with execution parameters.
4. **Execute AWS Batch Job:** Calls `awsexec(event)` to trigger the remote computation.
5. **Format Output Response:**
 - If `presigned_url_out` is `True`, a presigned URL for the output file is generated using `generate_presigned_url(water)`.
 - Returns a dictionary with the execution ID and the processed water depth file path.

Outputs

The function returns a tuple:

(mimetype, outputs)

Where:

- mimetype: Fixed as 'application/json'
- outputs: A dictionary with the following keys:

Key	Type	Description
Id	<i>string</i>	Identifier for the executed process.
water_depth_file	<i>string</i>	Path to the generated water depth file.
presigned_url (optional)	<i>string</i>	Presigned URL for accessing the output file.

Error Handling

- If user authentication fails, returns:

```
{ "id": "safer-rain-process", "message": "Invalid user or token" }
```

- Logs execution parameters and results for debugging and monitoring.

Example Usage

```
curl -X POST
"http://pygeoapi-SaferPlaces-lb-409838694.us-east-1.elb.amazonaws.com/processes/safer-rain-process/execution" \
```

```
-H "Content-Type: application/json" \
```

```
-d {
```

```
  "inputs": {
```

```
    "user": "user",
```

```
    "token": "token",
```

```
    "dem": "s3://path/to/dem.tif",
```

```
    "rain": 50,
```

```
    "water": "s3://path/to/output.tif",
```

```
    "debug": true,
```

```
    "presigned_url_out": true
```

```
  }
```

```
}
```

AWS serverless operations

To provide scalability and reliability, the SaferPlaces API extensively relies on serverless functions like AWS Lambda and AWS Batch. After parsing and validating the input data, the PyGeoAPI process triggers AWS Batch or Lambda to run the requested simulation. The request can be customized with specific execution settings, such as asynchronous or synchronous mode, allocated memory and CPU for the AWS Batch instance, and the number of retry attempts before termination.

Final thoughts

The SaferRainProcessor provides an efficient API for executing rainfall impact simulations. It integrates with AWS Batch and AWS Lambda for high-performance processing and ensures security with user authentication mechanisms. Developers can use this documentation to understand its inputs, execution process, and expected outputs.

SaferDATA API Documentation

This section documents SaferData as used in the Rimini Real-World Lab. It outlines the system architecture (PyGeoAPI on OGC standards), how processes are invoked via APIs, and how scheduled automation keeps datasets current. It then details data sources and variables, integration patterns (ingestor vs retriever), processing and storage conventions on S3, and the access interfaces with common inputs. Finally, it describes runtime scheduling logic, a usage footprint snapshot, and current limitations with planned improvements.

System Architecture Overview

The architecture of the data collection and pre-processing system deployed for the Rimini Real-World Lab is based on a PyGeoAPI server. This open-source framework provides a standardized way to publish and access geospatial data and processes through web services, fully aligned with OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) specifications.

In this system, each data type (e.g., rainfall, river levels, sea state) is managed through a dedicated PyGeoAPI Process, which is responsible for three main tasks:

1. **Extracting data** from external providers.
2. **Pre-processing** the raw information to harmonize and prepare it for further use.
3. **Storing** the processed outputs in a structured and accessible way.

API-Based Process Invocation

Each process can be **triggered via an API call** to the PyGeoAPI server.

These calls are parameterized, allowing users or automated services to customize the request by specifying:

- **Area of Interest (AOI)**, defined through a bounding box (bbox).
- **Temporal range**, to select data for a specific period.
- **Additional parameters**, which depend on the specific characteristics of the dataset (e.g., resolution, forecast steps, or provider-specific settings).

This design ensures flexibility and reusability, as the same process can serve different analytical and operational needs simply by adjusting its input parameters.

Automation Through Scheduled Jobs

Since each dataset is updated by its provider at different publication frequencies — ranging from every 5 minutes (e.g., radar precipitation data) to every 12 hours (e.g., some forecast models) — the system includes a layer of automation to ensure timely and consistent data acquisition.

This automation is orchestrated via scheduled jobs (e.g., cron), which periodically invoke the relevant processes.

- The cron jobs automatically populate the required parameters for each process call, following **pre-defined standards** agreed upon for the Rimini RWL use case.
- For example, the bounding box remains fixed for the project area, while temporal ranges are set according to the update frequency of each provider.

These configurations will be detailed in the following sections, where the individual providers and variables are described.

Key Design Benefits

- **Modularity**: each process is independent and dedicated to a specific data source, simplifying maintenance and future expansions.
- **Scalability**: new datasets can be integrated by simply adding a new process and corresponding cron job, without altering the core architecture.
- **Automation**: scheduled jobs ensure continuous data ingestion and pre-processing, minimizing the need for manual intervention.
- **Standardization**: parameter conventions guarantee consistency in data handling across different providers and update frequencies.

Data Sources and Variables

The system integrates heterogeneous datasets coming from multiple external providers, covering different temporal perspectives and thematic domains.

The data are classified into two main categories:

1. **Real-time data**, representing current conditions and very recent observations (within the same day).
2. **Forecast data**, providing short-term predictions of the expected conditions in the immediate future (also within the same day or slightly beyond).

Across both categories, the datasets are organized into three **scenarios** relevant to the Rimini Real-World Lab activities:

- **Pluvial**: rainfall and precipitation-related variables.
- **Fluvial**: river levels and river discharge.
- **Coastal**: sea level and wave conditions.

Real-Time Data Providers

These data sources provide continuous monitoring of current conditions, with updates ranging from every 5 minutes to every 30 minutes, depending on the variable and the sensor network.

Provider	Variable(s)	Update Frequency	Scenario
Italian Civil Protection Department (DPC)	Surface Rainfall Intensity (SRI).	Every 5 min	Pluvial
ARPAE Sensor Network	Total precipitation, river discharge, tidal, wave height and wave direction	Every 10–30 min, depending on sensor	Pluvial / Fluvial / Coastal
HERA Radar (via Hypermeteo)	Rainfall radar observations	Every 5 min	Pluvial

Forecast Data Providers

The forecast data sources focus on **near-future predictions**, enabling proactive decision-making by anticipating potential critical events.

Update frequencies vary significantly depending on the model, from **every 5 minutes** for high-resolution nowcasting to **daily runs** for longer-horizon forecasts.

Provider	Variable(s)	Forecast Horizon	Update Frequency	Scenario
ICON-2I Model	Precipitation forecast	Up to 72 hours	Two runs per day (12h) (forecast every hour)	Pluvial
Meteoblue	Precipitation forecast on a gridded tile network	Up to 14 days	Every 5 min	Pluvial
Hypermeteo Now Radar	Short-term precipitation nowcasting	Next 3 hours	Every 5 min	Pluvial
SWANMER Model	Wave height forecast	Up to 72 hours	Daily run (hourly forecast steps)	Coastal
ADRIAC Model	Sea level forecast	Up to 72 hours	Daily run (forecast every 10 min)	Coastal

Integration into the System

For each data source, one or more PyGeoAPI Processes are configured and operated to manage the entire workflow, from acquisition to dissemination.

The exact configuration depends on the nature of the data and the size of the files provided by the source:

- **Retriever Process (most common case)**
 - For high-frequency data streams (e.g., radar, sensors), only a **retriever process** is configured.
 - These datasets are updated very frequently and consist of relatively small files.
 - The process directly connects to the provider each time it is invoked, retrieves only the portion of data needed, and immediately prepares the output for storage and dissemination.
 - This approach avoids unnecessary storage of large amounts of data while ensuring near real-time availability.
- **Ingestor + Retriever Process (for large forecast products)**

- For some forecast models, such as ICON-2I, SWANMER, and ADRIAC, the data generated in each run are large and complex products.
- In these cases, an ingestor process is used to configured to acquire the entire dataset once per model run and store it in a structured format.
- The retriever process then operates on this locally stored dataset, extracting only the required subset based on the parameters provided (e.g., bounding box and time window).
- This two-step approach optimizes performance by avoiding repeated large downloads and ensures rapid responses when serving specific requests.

For the Rimini RWL use case, these processes are automated through cron jobs, which periodically invoke them with pre-defined standard parameters, such as a fixed bounding box and time windows aligned with each provider's update frequency.

This setup ensures reliable and consistent ingestion while minimizing manual intervention.

While the current configuration is tailored to the Rimini Real-World Lab, all processes can also be triggered manually or customized for other applications by supplying different input parameters.

Data Processing and Storage Structure

The output of each process is always a geospatial dataset, meaning that every piece of information is linked to specific spatial and temporal dimensions.

Depending on the nature of the source data, the resulting dataset may take different structural forms, either vector or raster.

Data Formats

- **Vector Data (e.g., sensors)**

For datasets coming from sensor networks (e.g., ARPAE stations), the resulting files are structured as GeoJSON Feature Collections.

- Each feature represents a specific sensor or measurement point.
- The time series for the monitored variable is encapsulated in a property, represented as a list of pairs:
(*timestamp*, *value*).

- This structure allows for compact representation and easy integration with time-series analysis tools.

- **Raster Data (e.g., radar and forecast models)**
For gridded data such as radar imagery or model outputs (ICON-2I, SWANMER, ADRIAC), the chosen format is GeoTIFF.
 - The files are multi-band rasters, where each band corresponds to a distinct time step.
 - This enables efficient handling of temporal sequences, such as precipitation forecasts or sea level simulations.

Storage Structure in S3 Buckets

All datasets are stored in Amazon S3 buckets, following a hierarchical naming structure that ensures consistency and facilitates access.

The hierarchy is organized as follows:

/PROVIDER/

/VARIABLE/

PROVIDER__VARIABLE__TIMESTAMP

- **Provider Level:**

The top-level prefix corresponds to the data provider (e.g., DPC, ARPAAE, Hypermeteo).

- **Variable Level:**

Within each provider folder, there is a sub-folder for each variable.

- Most providers manage a single variable.
- Some, such as ARPAAE, have multiple variables grouped under separate sub-folders.

- **File Naming Convention:**

The files are named according to the following convention:

PROVIDER__VARIABLE__TIMESTAMP

Where:

- PROVIDER identifies the data source.
- VARIABLE specifies the measured or predicted parameter.

- **TIMESTAMP** provides a clear temporal reference, which is interpreted differently depending on the type of data:
 - **Real-time data:** the timestamp corresponds to the latest time value contained in the file.
 - This represents the moment when the dataset reflects what has happened during the preceding observation window.
 - *Example:* A file with a timestamp of 12:00 shows the conditions observed up to that exact time.
 - **Forecast data:** the timestamp corresponds to the earliest time value contained in the file.
 - This represents the starting point of the forecast, from which future conditions are predicted.
 - *Example:* A file with a timestamp of 12:00 contains predictions from 12:00 onward, covering the next hours or days.

This distinction is fundamental to interpreting the datasets correctly, as it clearly differentiates between observed past conditions and projected future scenarios.

Purpose and Benefits of the Storage Design

This structured approach to data storage serves several important purposes:

- **Clarity and traceability:** Each file can be uniquely identified by its provider, variable, and reference time, avoiding ambiguities.
- **Scalability:** New variables or providers can be added without restructuring the system, simply by introducing additional prefixes.
- **Efficiency in retrieval:** Applications and processes can easily filter and access exactly the data they need, thanks to predictable paths and standardized naming conventions.
- **Support for automation:** The bucket structure is designed to work seamlessly with automated pipelines and external services that consume the data through APIs or scheduled processes.

API & Access Interfaces

All data access is exposed through OGC API – Processes (PyGeoAPI).

Each process is discoverable at `.../processes/{process-id}` and executable via:

- Synchronous execution: `POST .../processes/{id}/execution` with JSON body:

```
{ "inputs": { /* parameters */ } }
```

Common inputs (shared semantics)

Input	Type	Meaning / Usage
Token	string	Authentication / identification.
lat_range	[lat_min, lat_max]	Latitude filter in EPSG:4326.
long_range	[lon_min, lon_max]	Longitude filter in EPSG:4326.
time_range	[start_iso, end_iso]	Temporal window (ISO8601). Constraints vary per process (e.g., within last week; or “now → +3h” for nowcast).
strict_time_range	boolean	If true, validates that data exist up to the requested end time. Default false.
out_format	string	Output format (process-specific: e.g., geojson, dataframe, json, netcdf).
Debug	boolean	Enables verbose diagnostics.

Note: Some processes also accept granularity helpers such as `time_delta` (minutes, often multiple of 5) and, for models, `forecast_run` and/or `run_time` (ISO run timestamps).

Process mini-cards (inputs & outputs)

ARPAE — *ARPAE realtime data Process* (arpae-realtime-process)

Type: Retriever (vector, sensors)

Inputs (in addition to common):

- `variable_codes` (list of codes):

- "B13011" total_precipitation
 - "B13215" river_level
 - "B13226" river_discharge
 - "B22037" tidal_national_ref
 - "B22070" wave_height_significative
 - "B22073" wave_height_max
 - "B22001" wave_direction
- station_names (dict): keys = variable codes, values = list of station names (case-insensitive exact match).
 - out_format: geojson (*default, recommended*) or dataframe.

Outputs:

status, s3_uri (station GeoJSON), type (e.g., FeatureCollection), features (sensor features with time series in properties), metadata, crs (CRS84/EPSSG:4326).

DPC — DPC Radar Rainfall Process (dpc-radar-rainfall-process)

Type: Retriever (raster, real-time radar SRI)

Inputs (in addition to common):

out_format: netcdf | json | dataframe.

Outputs:

status, s3_uri (merged timestamp multiband raster), data (in requested out_format).

HERA/Hypermeteo — Radar Rainfall Process (hera-radar-rainfall-process)

Type: Retriever (raster, real-time radar)

Inputs (in addition to common):

time_delta (minutes, multiple of 5; default 5),

out_format: netcdf | json | dataframe.

Outputs:

status, s3_uri (merged timestamp multiband raster), data.

Hypermeteo — *NowRadar Rainfall Process* (now-radar forecast)

Type: Retriever (raster, **nowcast** precipitation)

Inputs (in addition to common):

time_range must be **from current time up to max +3h**,

time_delta (minutes, multiple of 5; default 5),

out_format: netcdf | json | dataframe.

Outputs:

status, s3_uri, data.

Meteoblue — *Precipitation Retriever* (meteoblue forecast)

Type: Retriever (gridded forecasts)

Inputs (in addition to common):

- service: basic-5min (*default*) | basic-1h
- grid_res: meters, multiple of 100 (default 1000)
- time_delta: minutes (aligned to service granularity)

Outputs:

status, collected_data (array of objects with date and S3_uri).

ICON-2I — *Precipitation Ingestor* (icon2i-precipitation-ingestor-process)

Type: Ingestor (forecast, large product)

Inputs (in addition to common):

forecast_run: ISO string or list; at 00:00:00 or 12:00:00; **≥ 2 days ago** if provided (otherwise “all available from current date”).

Outputs:

status, collected_data (list of {date, S3_uri} for stored runs).

ICON-2I — *Precipitation Retriever* (icon2i-precipitation-retriever-process)

Type: Retriever (subset from ingested ICON-2I)

Inputs (in addition to common):

out_format: netcdf | json | dataframe.

(Spatial window via lat_range/long_range; time window via time_range.)

Outputs:

status, s3_uri (merged multiband raster), data (time-series dataset in requested format).

SWANEMR — *Wave Height Ingestor* (swanemr-waveheight-ingestor-process)

Type: Ingestor (forecast, large product)

Inputs (in addition to common):

forecast_run: ISO at 00:00:00 or 12:00:00; **≥ 1 week ago** if provided (otherwise “all available from current date”).

Outputs:

status, collected_data ({date, S3_uri}).

SWANEMR — *Wave Height Retriever* (swanemr-waveheight-retriever-process)

Type: Retriever (subset from ingested SWANEMR; coastal)

Inputs (in addition to common):

sample_points: [[lon, lat], ...] (EPSG:4326) — optional, to return a sample GeoJSON,

out_format: netcdf | json | dataframe.

Outputs:

status, s3_uri, data (wave-height time series in requested format).

ADRIAC — *Sea Level Ingestor* (adriac-sealevel-ingestor-process)

Type: Ingestor (forecast, large product)

Inputs (in addition to common):

forecast_run: ISO at 00:00:00; ≥ 1 week ago if provided (otherwise “all available from current date”).

Outputs:

status, collected_data ({date, S3_uri}).

ADRIAC — *Sea Level Retriever* (adriac-sealevel-retriever-process)

Type: Retriever (subset from ingested ADRIAC; coastal)

Inputs (in addition to common):

sample_points: [[lon, lat], ...] (EPSG:4326) — optional;

out_format: netcdf | json | dataframe.

Outputs:

status, s3_uri, data (sea-level time series in requested format).

How the Rimini RWL cron payloads are shaped

In production, the cron jobs submit compact base payloads (bbox, options, etc.).

At runtime, a small scheduler function adds time-dependent parameters (e.g., rolling time_range, or the model forecast_run window) based on current UTC and provider cadence.

Runtime time-logic (summary by process)

- **HERA radar (hera-radar-rainfall-process)**
 - Round to nearest 5'; time_range = [now-5h, now-5']

- **DPC radar (dpc-radar-rainfall-process)**
 - Round to nearest 5'; apply a +10' safety delay; time_range = [now-5h-10', now-10']

- **ARPAE realtime (arpae-realtime-process)**
 - Round to nearest 5'; delay depends on variable:
 - precipitation B13011 or river level B13215: 15'
 - tidal ref B22037: 30'
 - wave dir B22001 or wave height B22070: 40'
 - time_range = [now-12h-delay, now-delay]

- **ICON-2I ingestor (icon2i-precipitation-ingestor-process)**
 - Floor hour to multiple of 12; forecast_run = [run-12h, run] (two latest runs)

- **ICON-2I retriever (icon2i-precipitation-retriever-process)**
 - Round hour to h:00; time_range = [now, now+5h]

- **SWANEMR ingestor (swanemr-waveheight-ingestor-process)**
 - Use day boundary; forecast_run = [yesterday@00:00, today@00:00]

- **SWANEMR retriever (swanemr-waveheight-retriever-process)**
 - Round hour to h:00; time_range = [now, now+5h]

- **ADRIAC ingestor (adriac-sealevel-ingestor-process)**
 - Use day boundary; forecast_run = [yesterday@00:00, today@00:00]

- **ADRIAC retriever (adriac-sealevel-retriever-process)**
 - Round to nearest 10'; time_range = [now, now+5h]

- **Meteoblue retriever (meteoblue-precipitation-retriever-process)**
 - Round to nearest 5'; time_range = [now, now+5h]

- **NowRadar forecast (nowradar-precipitation-process)**
 - Round to nearest 5'; limit to next +3h; time_range = [now, now+3h]

This logic guarantees we always query stable intervals (with appropriate delay buffers) and keep forecast horizons consistent with each provider's native cadence.

Why this matters (interpretation & reproducibility)

- **Reproducible subsets:** The fixed bbox and time windows make the outputs consistent for the Rimini AOI.
- **Provider alignment:** Delay buffers (e.g., DPC +10'; ARPAE variable-dependent) prevent partial tiles/records.
- **Performance:** Forecast ingestors store full runs once; retrievers slice quickly on demand.
- **Clarity:** The same JSON structure can be re-used by third parties, simply swapping bbox/time parameters or the service options.

Final thoughts

The Rimini Real-World Lab now operates a standardized, API-driven data pipeline (PyGeoAPI + processes) that reliably ingests, harmonizes, and serves real-time and short-term forecast datasets across pluvial, fluvial, and coastal scenarios.

The split between ingestor (full model runs) and retriever (on-demand spatial/temporal subsets) has proven effective: it reduces bandwidth and latency for heavy products (ICON-2I, SWANEMR, ADRIAC) while keeping high-frequency sources responsive (DPC, HERA, ARPAE, CAE, nowcasting services).

Data are organized and time-stamped coherently in S3, enabling reproducible analyses and direct reuse by the web platform and simulations. The appendix provides stable, copy-pasteable payloads for third-party adoption.

Data collected to date (as of 2025-09-15)

Bucket: s3://SaferPlaces.co/Directed/process_out/ — 116,126 objects, 34.3 GB

Provider/Folder	Size	Objects
ADRIAC	21.5 GB	16,726
DPC	9.0 GB	43,647

Meteoblue	2.0 GB	9,880
SWANEMR	839.9 MB	3,895
ARPAE_realtime	406.0 MB	34,265
ICON_2I	248.1 MB	1,683
RADAR_HERA_150M_5MIN	177.6 MB	518
CAE	222.6 MB	5,512

At a glance

- Storage is dominated by ADRIAC (~62.6%) and DPC (~26.2%); Meteoblue ~5.8%, SWANEMR ~2.4%.
- Object count is driven by DPC (~37.6%) and ARPAE (~29.5%), reflecting high-frequency updates and sensor granularity.
- This footprint is consistent with our design: heavy forecast runs stored once (ingestors), frequent small increments for real-time sources (retrievers).

Current Limitations

Use the following list as an operational guide to constraints that affect data timeliness, comparability, and cost. Limits arise from provider cadence, model horizons, heterogeneous resolutions, and infrastructure throughput. They impact scheduling (delays and buffers), analytics (alignment and reprojection), storage policy (lifecycle/pruning), and API behavior (quotas, authentication). Each item flags the issue, why it occurs, and the practical implications for process configuration and downstream use.

- **Provider latency & freshness**
Data timeliness varies by source; we apply safety delays (e.g., 10' on DPC, variable-based on ARPAE) to avoid partial datasets, at the cost of a small lag.
- **Heterogeneous coverage & resolution**
Spatial/temporal resolutions differ (sensors vs radar vs models), requiring harmonization when comparing sources.
- **Forecast horizon constraints**
Near-term nowcasts (e.g., **NowRadar** up to +3 h) vs short-term models (e.g., **ICON-2I/SWANEMR/ADRIAC** ~72 h) limit certain scenarios.

- **Time alignment across sources**
Different step sizes (5', 10', 60') can introduce alignment issues for multi-source analyses without resampling.
- **CRS & reprojection**
Outputs are standardized to EPSG:4326; on-the-fly reprojection is not exposed in all processes.
- **Storage growth & cost**
Full-run ingestors (ICON-2I, SWANEMR, ADRIAC) generate sizeable archives; lifecycle and pruning policies are important.
- **Compute & I/O during ingestion**
Large model runs are bandwidth/CPU intensive; concurrency must be tuned to avoid throttling.
- **Error handling & partial data**
strict_time_range trades completeness vs availability; unavailable tail data can produce empty or truncated windows if enforced strictly.
- **Access, quotas & licensing**
Some providers require tokens and have ToS/quotas (e.g., Meteoblue); misuse can trigger rate limiting.
- **Metadata consistency**
Variable names/units differ (e.g., ARPAE codes); consistent metadata mapping is essential for downstream users.
- **Process-specific constraints**
Example: **CAE retriever** needs filters.instrument; coastal retrievers optionally use sample_points for point series.

Future Developments & Opportunities

Use the following list as a roadmap for planned enhancements that improve discoverability, robustness, and analytical capability. Items focus on cataloguing standards, automated QA/QC, aggregation and analytics APIs, and timeline harmonization across sources. Each line indicates what will be added, why it matters for reproducibility and throughput, and how it simplifies downstream analyses.

- **Cataloging & discoverability**
Publish datasets/runs via **STAC / OGC Records**, enrich provenance/lineage metadata.

- **Quality control & reliability**
Automated QA/QC (gap detection, range checks), per-run health signals, retry/backoff policies, alerting on ingestion failures.
- **Aggregation & analytics APIs**
New processes for spatial/temporal stats (sum/mean/max), accumulations, exceedance, return periods.
- **Harmonized timelines**
Utility services for time resampling/alignment across sources (5'/10'/60'), easing composite analyses.

Chat-driven AI Agent for Data Access & Decision Support (*flagship initiative*)

This flagship concept adds a chat-driven interface layer that leverages PyGeoAPI processes and the S3 catalogue to translate user intent into reproducible data operations. Build a conversational agent that sits on top of PyGeoAPI and the S3 catalogue to **query, visualize, and analyse** datasets via natural language, which are accessible to both technicians and non-technical stakeholders.

- **Natural-language to data:** “Show rainfall over Rimini last 2 hours” → executes the right process, sets bbox/time, returns maps/series.
- **On-the-fly visuals & summaries:** auto-generate charts, quick maps, and incident-ready briefs (PDF/HTML) with clear citations/metadata.
- **Built-in analytics:** accumulations, exceedances vs thresholds, short-term scenario comparisons, simple risk indicators.
- **Impact:** shortens time-to-insight for emergency workflows, broadens adoption beyond specialists, and creates a compelling, fundable product surface

Partners

